

CONDENSATION OF *o*-, *m*-, AND *p*-NITROBENZALDEHYDES WITH MALONIC ACID IN THE PRESENCE OF ORGANIC BASES.

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Aldehydes have been condensed with malonic acid using a mixture of pyridine (1 mol.) and piperidine (traces) by Haworth, Perkin and Rankin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1693) and by Dutt (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1, 297) and a few other bases each in molecular proportions (Dalal and Dutt, *ibid.*, 1932, 9, 309). The pyridine-piperidine method, originally given by Haworth, Perkin and Rankin (*loc. cit.*) and modified by Robinson and Shinoda (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1693) has been applied by Chakravarti, Haworth and Perkin, who using *m*-methoxybenzaldehyde and malonic acid (1 : 3 mols.) in pyridine (3.5 mols.) and a trace of piperidine (5 c.c. in 250 c.c. of pyridine with 100 g. of aldehyde and 160 g. of malonic acid) report "an almost quantitative yield" on heating.

Work in these laboratories has shown that such excessive proportions of the base and of malonic acid are not essential and that these condensations are, as well, even much better carried out, when for one molecule of the aldehyde, only one of the acid and 0.15-0.25 mol. of pyridine or a similar base are used (Kurien and Pandya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 824; Ali, Kurien and Pandya, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1935, 1A, 440; Pandya and Vahidy, *ibid.*, 1935, 2A, 402; 1936, 4A, 134, 140, 144; 1937, 6A, 437, 181).

It has been generally found that not only does the condensation take place very easily but also that the product is much purer and is obtained in greater yields, which are often quantitative. It has also been observed that the action of the base is truly catalytic as even in its absence the reaction proceeds, but very slowly and the yields are much less.

In this paper the condensations of *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes have been studied under the same conditions. Dalal and Dutt (*loc. cit.*) obtained *o*-nitrocinnamic acid by heating a mixture of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde and malonic acid for 9 hours on a water-bath in the presence of quinoline (mol. proportion), but the yield was only 44.4%.

Dutt (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1, 300) condensed *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde and malonic acid in the presence of pyridine (1 mol.) and traces of piperidine in 90% yield. Dalal and Dutt (*loc. cit.*) obtained the same acid

in 82.5% yield by heating for 3/4 hours on a water-bath in the presence of quinoline (molecular proportion).

Dutt (*loc. cit.*) obtained from *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde and malonic acid *p*-nitrocinnamic acid in 82% yield, using pyridine (1 mol.) and traces of piperidine. Dala and Dutt (*loc. cit.*) obtained the same acid in about 75% yield by heating *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde and malonic acid for 3 hours on a water-bath in the presence of quinoline.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The condensations were carried out exactly following the method of Pandya (*J. Indian Chem., Soc.*, 1934, 11, 824, *et. seq.*).

TABLE I.

Catalyst	Amount of catalyst = 0.15 mol.					
	<i>o</i> -Nitro-		<i>m</i> -Nitro-		<i>p</i> -Nitro-	
1. Pyridine	1.75 g.	(90.67%)	1.70 g.	(80.08%)	1.69 g.	(87.56%)
2. Piperidine	1.75	(88.08)	1.65	(85.49)	1.64	(84.97)
3. Quinoline	1.60	(82.90)	1.55	(80.35)	1.45	(75.12)
4. Without base.	1.00	(51.80)	1.02	(52.84)	1.00	(51.85)

The products from *o*- and *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde are colourless and the product from *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde is light yellow in colour in all these cases.

Thus *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes undergo condensation with malonic acid very readily on heating on the water-bath and the reaction is very nearly completed in 4 hours in the presence of a trace of pyridine, piperidine and quinoline but it takes a much longer time in the absence of any base, when the yield in 4 hours comes up to about 40% only.

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